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INTENSIFICATION OF THE PROCESS OF TRAINING SPECIALISTS IN CULTURAL UNIVERSITIES THROUGH THE USE OF MODERN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract: *The main problems of introducing information technologies in higher education are considered, their importance for the effectiveness of training library personnel.*

Keywords: *information technology, pedagogy, training, higher education, libraries.*

One of the important conditions for the introduction of information technologies in higher education is its professional focus. The professional basis is the need to prepare students for such activities that require skills in using new technologies. Therefore, students of the Faculty of Library and Information Management of GIJKUz, in accordance with the new educational programs being introduced, need to obtain knowledge in the field of information and telecommunication technologies. In modern society, libraries are turning into information and resource centers, their activities and further development depend on the corresponding professional level of librarians. Searching on the Internet, training users, working with electronic resources are becoming mandatory requirements for the qualifications of a librarian.

In Uzbekistan, increased attention is paid to the development of the social sphere, education and science. This is especially true for higher education, which is subject to change depending on the demands of modern society. It should be noted that “the number of higher education institutions in Uzbekistan has increased from 77 to 211 in seven years, including 30 branches of foreign universities, 65 non-state higher education institutions, the coverage of the population with higher education in the country has increased from 9 to 42%” [2, p. 1].

A promising way to intensify the integrated educational process and increase its efficiency is to introduce ideas, methods and means of information, namely automated teaching aids.

At present, it can be argued that the saturation of the educational process using new information technologies requires good systemic representations. The theory and practice of creating automated information systems show the need to adhere to systemic skills in their design and use. Systematicity is manifested in the methodological plan, in plans for setting tasks for automating the development of algorithmic and software tools and their practical use. The view on the problems of information processing should be broader, more systematic and dynamic, taking into account the influence of information processing processes on the social environment. This provision defines one of the most important conditions for the formation of the qualifications of library staff in terms of their systematic training.

The modern stage of education has put forward the idea of humanization of education and a personality-oriented approach to the essence of the content of education [5, p.9]. With this

approach, the focus is on the individual. In the course of implementing this approach, the educational, spiritual, cultural and vital needs of the individual are satisfied. The determining factors are a humane attitude towards the individual, the unhindered development of his individual abilities and the possibility of more complete self-realization in the cultural and educational space.

The success of all library and information activities depends significantly on the training of library personnel. And vice versa, modern technologies set standards and requirements for universities to train specialists. It is no coincidence that it was precisely from practitioners that the wishes came in accordance with which students at the Institute of Culture began to receive the knowledge necessary to work with technical means and software that have found application in library and information institutions.

Naturally, the quality of training specialists for library and information institutions in cultural colleges, pedagogical colleges and universities will depend on the state of the technical level of the organization of the educational process. It will be necessary to introduce automated training systems (ATS), automated workstations (AWP) based on the developments used in the activities of modern libraries everywhere in this process.

It is possible to speak about the proper level of higher professional education only if students are involved in this process. Such activity presupposes the students' activity in obtaining, processing and using the acquired knowledge. Whatever methods are used in teaching, it is important to create such psychological conditions in which the student would take an active position and could fully express himself as a subject of educational activity. Innovative technologies in professional education contribute to improving the quality of education.

The peculiarity of active teaching methods is the ability to obtain basic knowledge independently by working with educational materials outside of the classroom, but for this, appropriate provision of information for students must be created. In addition to traditional textbooks and teaching aids, it is necessary to use an electronic form of presentation of educational information. Its advantages are, first of all, its compactness, the use of such means of presentation of educational material as video, sound, animation, interactivity. No less important is the fact that the student can test the knowledge acquired independently.

The impact of digitalization on library and information activities and their subjects is recognized by library theorists and practitioners around the world. A study of international experience in digitalization of library activities has shown that it is aimed at changing the mentality of library staff, since it is the change in professional thinking that contributes to the change in the role of the library in society. Of interest in this regard is the project "Advancing Digital Empowerment of Libraries in Europe" (ADELE) (<https://www.adele-project.eu/>), which is a specialized consortium of organizations designed to help libraries undergo digital transformation. Experts representing libraries and educational institutions are working on the creation of a web tool that helps libraries assess their position in the field of using digital technologies from the point of view of managers, library staff and library users.

Among the authors who deeply and comprehensively study the processes of digital transformation are Russian figures in library practice and education: A. I. Borovinsky, N. I. Gendina, E. N. Guseva, V. K. Klyuev, M. Yu. Neshcheret, N. S. Redkina, V. K. Stepanov, N. A. Stefanovskaya, I. P. Tikunova and others. The researchers note the inadequacy of theoretical and methodological research into the problems of digitalization and digital transformation in the library sphere, the need

for a significant update of the content of educational programs implemented in universities [1, p. 146].

Currently, the educational process at the university faces the following challenges: providing unlimited network access to educational materials, access to databases, electronic publications, digital libraries, interactive interaction via high-speed local networks, transmission of voice and visual information, and many others. Since 2018, the following digital projects have been implemented in a number of European libraries and in the USA: “Learning circles in libraries”, “FinLit” (“Financial literacy through public libraries”), “Cultural Heritage of the Future”, “3D Printing Support Service Project” (INNO3D), and the “COLIBLITE” project (“Community Libraries and Digital Literacy Skills for Children from Migrant and Lower-Income Families”) [6]. All this contributed to the creation and active use of educational multimedia technologies and educational resources on the Internet and, with the assistance of libraries, to gain access to useful online content, improve users' learning skills, increase their level of financial literacy, promote active participation of the population in the preservation and consumption of cultural heritage, and develop competencies in the field of SD printing. At the same time, teachers have the opportunity to quickly make corrections and additions to the educational material, as well as use new methods of delivering information to students - through special archives on servers, by e-mail and educational WEB pages, as well as in the form of electronic libraries. The training of specialists is based on a certain set of professional competencies, mobility in responding to the needs of library practice and the active participation of employers in the process of forming professional personnel of a new formation. At the bachelor's level, this is the formation and organization of the use of documentary resources of society; meeting public information needs; optimization of the functioning of library and information networks and systems; the use of modern ICT in library and information activities [7, p.65].

Communication tools provide the broadest opportunities for professional training: prompt transmission of information of any volume and type over different distances, interactivity and prompt feedback, organization of joint telecommunication projects, request for information on any issue of interest through the electronic conference system, etc. The social component of computerization of the educational process is manifested in the change in the functions of the teacher and the student, in the change in the attitude of the teacher and the student to the means of teaching and to each other.

The efficiency of classroom work is significantly increased by using electronic presentation of lecture material. Moving away from the traditional form of conducting a lesson, using a board, chalk and posters, the teacher receives a modern tool for presenting information in a variety of forms: text, graphic, animated, audio, video. At the same time, firstly, the quality and degree of mastering the educational material increases, secondly, the time for reproducing information is reduced, which saves it for explaining the material.

Conducting laboratory classes using information technologies presented in the local network allows to activate the work of students, and also gives the opportunity to control knowledge, discuss and analyze it together in the future. But this form of training requires the development of electronic individual assignments for students, contributing to an in-depth study of the material. This is due to the fact that among the sources of information, along with traditional ones, electronic information products have taken a strong place, the work with which requires special training. The creation of such training programs presupposes the presence of qualified employees, programmers, without their participation it is difficult for teachers to independently implement new projects in the field of

library and information education, and there are practically no methodological developments for their implementation. The created educational and methodological publications, as a rule, cannot be effectively used in modern education, including distance education. Completely new forms of electronic teaching aids and textbooks are required, allowing you to update their content, promptly providing students with the necessary educational materials on the studied academic disciplines. The existing desire of teachers to improve the level and quality of education will contribute to the creation of necessary information products, and this, ultimately, will improve the level of training of specialists in higher education institutions in the field of "Library and Information Activities".

The use of modern information technologies has a number of advantages:

- clarity;
- increasing the level of knowledge and reinforcing skills;
- reducing the study time for mastering the subject;
- improving the culture of the educational process;
- freeing up the teacher's time for creative work;
- transition to a system of personalized learning.

The introduction of methods and tools in the field of information technology in all spheres of society is associated with the need to change technology in order to improve the quality and productivity of labor, as well as with the search for a new resource of society, namely information. The information resource of society has become a reality, which causes the prevalence and growth of employees engaged in information processing. Accordingly, the system of higher education and training of specialists in cultural universities is changing, taking into account the increasing introduction of information technology into the learning process. Library education faces the task of preparing a multifunctional specialist who confidently owns printed and digital materials, combining work with content and services.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the most important issues remain those of providing higher education institutions with the appropriate technical means and personnel, and organizing scientific research by teachers to improve teaching methods based on the widespread use of information technology in the educational process.

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